

PERFORMANCE EMLPOYEE BUILT FROM TIME DISCIPLINE, RESPONSIBILITY AND REGULATIONS DISCIPLINE PG KEBON AGUNG MALANG

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Abstract:

This research was motivated with consideration that discipline can affect to performance of employee. This study is a quantitative research with a discipline variable and performance employee variable. Data collection technique were used in this research is a questionnaire is distributed to 75 respondent. The data were processed by software SPSS 23 for windows. The testing instrument it used validity test and reliability test. While for the data analysis technique was used descriptive test and multiple linear regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis it used because in this research more than two variable indicator, with F test, T test, and R² test. The result showed that from the third variable time discipline, responsibility discipline and regulatory discipline together can affect to performance of employee. From SPSS 23 analysis, time discipline variables have the most significant or dominant influence on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang.

Key words: Performance Employee, Time Discipline, Responsibility and Regulator Discipline

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Background

Acompany in carrying out its activities, both companies engaged in manufacturing and services will try to achieve the goals set previously. One thing that must be considered together is that the success of various activities within the company in achieving its goals depends not only on technological excellence, available operational funds, facilities or infrastructure owned, but also depends on aspects of human resources.

Work discipline is very important for the growth of an organization; "discipline is the awareness and willingness of a person to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms". So a good discipline will reflect the magnitude of an employee's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him both individually and in groups, so that it will be able to produce good performance (Hasibuan, 2013).

High employee performance is not only realized through expertise and skills in completing work but also through disciplined behavior patterns, so that it will produce a good and optimal work that can be given to the company. Thus it can be said that good employee performance is an employee who has good work discipline and expertise in in its field, so that it can produce a good and profitable performance for the company (Armstrong, M and Baron, A., 2004).

Kebon Agung Sugar Factory or abbreviated as PG. Kebon Agung Malang is an industry engaged in sugar cane grinding located in JL. Cirebon Agung 1 Malang. Good performance

needs to be done by employees of PG Kebon Agung Malang by carrying out work discipline in accordance with the rules that apply in the company environment, because the activities carried out every day are quite dense. This can be seen from the capacity of the sugarcane reaching 10,000 tons of sugar cane per day.

Thus requiring all sections to work in a very disciplined and timely manner especially the Financial Administration (TUK). The section regulates the course of the company's operations such as auctions, distribution of goods distribution, regulates all administrative activities in charge of carrying out oversight of financial entry and exit as well as solving the financial problems of the factory or the whole company, staffing, and security. If the section does not carry out its duties properly it will hamper the company's operational activities.

Every employee at PG. Kebon Agung Malang needs an understanding of work discipline. If the work discipline has been implemented well, it will be able to reduce operational costs such as unnecessary expenses for overtime employees, minimize the use of electricity and office equipment, reduce the risk of work accidents, and other costs. That way, the results of the work produced will also be effective and will help or support the company's ultimate goal of maximum profit and will form a good employee performance.

2. Problem Formulation

1. How does the simultaneous influence of time discipline, responsibility and regulation on employee performance at PG Kebon Agung Malang?
2. How is the influence of time discipline, responsibility, and regulations partially on employee performance at PG Kebon Agung Malang?

3. Hypothesis

The conceptual model is an abstraction about a phenomenon that is formulated on the basis of generalization, while the hypothesis is a temporary answer to the formulation of a research problem, where the research problem formulation has been stated in the form of sentence questions. The hypothesis in this study is as follows.

Figure 1. Model of hypothesis research

1. Variable time discipline has a significant effect on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang

2. Variable responsibility discipline has a significant effect on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang
3. Variable regulatory discipline have a significant effect on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang
4. Time discipline variables have the most significant / dominant influence on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on the expert opinion that: “organizations need highly performing individuals in order to meet their goals, to deliver the products and services they specialized in, and finally to achieve competitive advantage. Performance is also important for the individual. Accomplishing tasks and performing at a high level can be a source of satisfaction, with feelings of mastery and pride. Low performance and not achieving the goals might be experienced as dissatisfying or even as a personal failure” (Sabine. S and M. Frese, 2005). And then it is also mentioned : “the human resource management implies a process containing several activities such as: design of scope of work, planning, staffing, training and development, performance evaluation, compensation system, relations with employee’s unions, etc. Each of these activities is important for successful human resources management. For example, planning of human resources is tightly connected to strategic and business planning in company” (Caiden and Becker G, 2005).

The goal of human resource management is as efficient as possible usage of them and achieving the highest possible economic effects. The importance of human resource management for the modern business enterprise, and the principles by witch modern management is guided determines the philosophy that man is the most valuable resource in the organization (Anderson, D. W., 1999). This resource is perceived as a potential and total power (competitive advantage) of the company. In this paper, author analyzed two important field connected with human resources and related to competitive advantage: changes and new business environment and value creation.

Moreover, “performance if it is recognized by others within the organization is often rewarded by financial and other benefits. Performance is a major although not the only prerequisite for future career development and success in the labor market. Although there might be exceptions, high performers get promoted more easily within an organization and generally have better career opportunities than low performers” (VanScotter, Motowidlo, & Cross, 2000; Sabine. S and M. Frese., 2005).

In this it explained that: “the high relevance of individual performance is also reflected in work and organizational psychological research. To get a clearer picture about the importance of individual performance in empirical research we conducted a literature search in the twelve of the major work and organizational psychology journals. These journals cover a broad range of individual, group-level and organizational-level phenomena” (Sabine. S and M. Frese., 2005).

Based on the expert opinion that: “a person who is trained to consider his actions, to undertake them deliberately, is in so far forth disciplined. Add to this ability a power to endure in an intelligently chosen course in face of distraction, confusion, and dculity, and you have the essence of discipline. Discipline is positive. To cow the spirit, to subdue inclination, to compel obedience, to mortify the flesh, to make a subordinate perform an uncongenial task - these things are not disciplinary according to the development of power to recognize what one is about and to persistence in accomplishment” (Dewey, 1916; Slee, Roger, 1997).

Some understanding of the discipline particularly from the perspective of the organization can be defined as an attitude that reflects adherence and accuracy against a rule that is in-personal nature to maintain that there is the existence of an organization. Good discipline shows the person's sense of responsibility towards the tasks given (Ranupandojo, 2010; Sarwani, 2016). The principles set forth disciplinary are: a). Disciplinary done privately. Disciplinary done by giving warning to the employee; b). Discipline must be constructive. In addition to providing warning and shows the errors made employees, must be accompanied by suggestions on how it should be done not to repeat the same mistakes; c). Discipline is lacking must be done directly with immediately. An action is performed immediately after proven that the employee had made a mistake; d). Fairness in discipline is indispensable. In the disciplinary action is carried out fairly and without favoritism (Simamora, 2011; Sarwani, 2016).

Discipline indicates a condition or comity that is in the employee of the rules and the accuracy of organization". Thus, if the rules or regulations that exist in the organization that are ignored or violated, the employee has poor discipline. Conversely, when employees adhere to the statutes of the organization, describes the condition of good discipline (Sutrisno, 2009).

Performance is a multi-dimensional concept. “On the most basic level, distinguish between task and contextual performance. Task performance refers to an individual’s proficiency with which he or she performs activities which contribute to the organization’s technical core” (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). In this it explained that : “this contribution can be both direct (e.g., in the case of production workers), or indirect (e.g., in the case of managers or staff personnel). Contextual performance refers to activities which do not contribute to the technical core but which support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which organizational goals are pursued” (Sabine. S and M. Frese., 2005).

Then it is also mentioned : “contextual performance includes not only behaviors such as helping coworkers or being a reliable member of the organization, but also making suggestions about how to improve work procedures. Three basic assumptions are associated with the differentiation between task and contextual performance” (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997; Motowidlo & Schmit, 1999; Sabine. S and M. Frese., 2005).

Task performance in itself is multi-dimensional. For example, among the eight performance components proposed by Campbell (1990), there are five factors which refer to task performance (cf. Campbell, Gasser, & Oswald, 1996; Motowidlo & Schmit, 1999; Sabine. S

and M. Frese., 2005). Each of these factors comprises a number of subfactors which may vary between different jobs. For example, the management/administration factor comprises subdimensions such as ; “(1) planning and organizing, (2) guiding, directing, and motivating subordinates and providing feedback, (3) training, coaching, and developing subordinates, (4) communication effectively and keeping others informed”.

Based on the expert opinion that : “in recent years, researchers paid attention to specific aspects of task performance. For example, innovation and customer-oriented behavior become increasingly important as organizations put greater emphasis on customer service” (Anderson & King, 1993; Bowen & Waldman, 1999; Sabine. S and M. Frese., 2005). Individual performance is not stable over time. Variability in an individual’s performance over time reflects; “(1) learning processes and other long-term changes and (2) temporary changes in performance. Individual performance changes as a result of learning. Studies showed that performance initially increases with increasing time spent in a specific job and later reaches a plateau”.

Moreover, the processes underlying performance change over time. “During early phases of skill acquisition, performance relies largely on ‘controlled processing’, the availability of declarative knowledge and the optimal allocation of limited attentional resources, whereas later in the skill acquisition process, performance largely relies on automatic processing, procedural knowledge, and psychomotor abilities” (Ackerman, 1988; Kanfer & Ackerman, 1989,). To identify the processes underlying changes of job performance, Murphy (1989) differentiated between a transition and a maintenance stage.

The maintenance stage occurs when the knowledge and skills needed to perform the job are learned and when task accomplishment becomes automatic. For performing during the transition phase, cognitive ability is highly relevant. During the maintenance stage, cognitive ability becomes less important and dispositional factors (motivation, interests, and values) increase in relevance (Azman, I. et al., 2014). Performance changes over time are not invariable across individuals. There is increasing empirical evidence that individuals differ with respect to patterns of intra-individual change (Hofmann, 1992; Hakel, 1998). These findings indicate that there is no uniform pattern of performance development over time.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative method, “explanatory design is typically used to explain and interpret quantitative results by collecting and analyzing follow-up quantitative data. Explanatory sequential mixed methods is one in which the researcher first conducts quantitative research, analyzes the results and then builds on the results to explain them in more detail with qualitative research. It is considered explanatory because the initial quantitative data results are explained further with the qualitative data” (Creswell, 2014).

Based on the expert opinion that: “explanatory is considered sequential because the initial quantitative phase is followed by the qualitative phase. This type of design is popular in fields with a strong quantitative orientation (hence the project begins with quantitative research),

but it presents challenges of identifying the quantitative results to further explore and the unequal sample sizes for each phase of the study” (Creswell, 2014).

This research was carried out in the Administration and Finance (TUK) section at PG Kebon Agung Malang office. The population in this study were employees in the Administration and Finance (TUK) section at PG Kebon Agung Malang as many as 75 respondent. The sample technique used is saturated sampling. Primary data collection using a questionnaire that was tested through validity and reliability tests. Analysis of research data using multiple linear regression data analysis with SPSS program.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents in the study (see table 1) had a variety of backgrounds ranging from gender, age, level of education and years of service as presented in the following table.

Table 1 Background Description of Respondents

No	Deskripsi Respondent	Amount	Persent (%)
1	Gender : Male	41	54,7
	Female	34	45,3
2	Age : 20 – 30 year	18	24,0
	31 – 40 year	42	56,0
	41 – 50 year	9	12,0
	> 50 year	6	8,0
3	Education : Elementary school	3	4,0
	Middle school	7	9,3
	High school graduate	20	26,7
	Bachelor	45	60,0
4	Really to : 5 year	7	9,3
	Work 5 – 10 year	19	25,3
	11 – 15 year	21	28,0
	> 15 year	28	37,3

Source: primary research data (2020)

Based on the table above it can be seen that the most male respondents were 54.7%, aged 31-40 years 56%, with undergraduate education 60% and work period of more than 15 years 37.3%.

Analysis of the research description (see table 2) for the data collected through a questionnaire of the research variables found that; time discipline has an average value of 3.59 which means good because it approaches the greatest value.

Table 2 Analyze description of the research variables

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Time Discipline (X ₁)	75	1.00	4.00	3.59

Responsibility Discipline (X ₂)	75	1.00	4.00	3.55
Regulator Discipline (X ₃)	75	1.00	4.00	3.67
Performance Employee (Y)	75	1.00	4.00	3.71

Source: primary research data (2020) Responsibility has an average value of 3.55 which also means good because it approaches the greatest value. Discipline in regulations has an average value of 3.67 which also means good because it is close to the greatest value. Then the employee's performance has an average value of 3.71 which also means good because it approaches the greatest value.

Table 3 Analyze validity and reliability of variables

Variable	N	Pearson Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha	Sig. (2-tailed)
Time Discipline (X ₁)	75	6.788	7.903	0.000
Responsibility Discipline (X ₂)	75	6.439	7.774	0.000
Regulator Discipline (X ₃)	75	6.221	7.205	0.000
Performance Employee (Y)	75	7.021	8.341	0.000

Source: primary research data (2020)

The instrument test results show the Pearson Correlation (r_{hitung}) value is greater than the standard value r_{table} (3,450) so that the instrument is declared valid with a significant 0,000. The reliability test obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value that was greater than the standard value of alpha 0.600 so that the instrument was declared reliable.

Table 4 Analyze Regression of variables

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.705 ^a	.641	.564	1.84355

a. Predictors: (Constant), Y

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.791	1.073		9.128	.000
	X.1	1.463	.287	.316	5.102	.000
	X.2	.712	.157	.247	4.544	.000
	X.3	.571	.202	.170	2.825	.036

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: primary research data (2020)

Based on table 4 of the results of the analysis of this study for the R Square value of 0.641, it means that the overall interpreter of the Time Discipline (X₁), Responsibility Discipline (X₂) and Regulator Discipline (X₃) to the Performance Employee (Y) is 64.1 % means that this influence is quite strong.

Partially it was found that the Time Discipline (X₁) variable had a significant effect ($p = 0,000$) with t 5,102 with beta 0,316. Then for the Responsibility Discipline (X₂) variable has a significant effect ($p = 0,000$) with t 4.544 and beta for 0.247. Finally, the Discipline

Regulator (X_3) also had a significant effect ($p = 0.036$) with t 2.825 and beta of 0.170. Based on the results of this analysis, Time Discipline (X_1) has the most significant or dominant influence on Performance Employees (Y).

Figure 2. Results hypothesis

The figure above shows that the research hypothesis is proven; “variable time discipline has a significant effect on employee performance employee, variable responsibility discipline has a significant effect on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang. Variable regulatory discipline have a significant effect on employee performance employee and time discipline variables have the most significant / dominant influence on employee performance employee PG Kebon Agung Malang”.

V. DISCUSSION

This study results that Time Discipline (X_1), Responsibility Discipline (X_2), and Regulator Discipline (X_3) have a significant effect on Performance Employee (Y) either partially or simultaneously. Time Discipline (X_1) variable has the most significant or dominant effect on Performance Employee (Y). Following up on the results of this research, the aspect that needs attention is. There are many things that are the focus of attention related to individual performance, where one of them is the work tdiscipline of members of the organization.

Figure 2: Model of Research Performance Employee, Time Discipline, Responsibility and Regulator Discipline

Work discipline is one of the important factors that play a role in determining the performance of organizational members because employees who have high discipline will

work in accordance with the rules and always try to complete the task well and on time. Work discipline is an attitude and action in obeying all the guidelines and regulations that have been determined to achieve organizational goals. Discipline is closely related to employee behavior and affects performance (Brown, D., 2011).

Self-discipline is like a muscle. We can grow and improve our strength with practice. But we can also grow tired and find our ability to remain in control exhausted. The more we use our self-control in a day, the more we find this resource depletes (Goldstein, 2016). Fortunately, as with our muscles, taking a break from your work is a simple strategy to regain that lost discipline and focus. We should schedule regular breaks, taking time to step away from desks or computers (Caiden and Becker G., 2005). In addition, leaders should schedule breaks that are appropriate to the work they tackle each day. For example, if you notice that certain tasks leave you drained or tired, consider scheduling this task at a time where you can immediately follow it with a long break or with work that requires little active self-control (Goldstein, 2016). Try to keep track of how your tasks make you feel.

Doing this will allow you to more effectively schedule your time to get the most out of your day and your self-control. Remember, the kinds of tasks that a leader finds particularly challenging or exhausting will differ across individuals. Your schedule for work and subsequent breaks should be personal to your own needs and interests (Goldstein, 2016). Like many skills, self-discipline is best improved with frequent practice. It is a learned behavior, not an inherent ability that we can train ourselves to engage in it more often. One of the best ways to set yourself up for success is to remove the things that you find distract you from your work (Campbell, J. P., 1999). This may look different across individuals. For some, shutting the door to their office may be enough to help sustain their attention. For others, silencing emails, turning off cell phones, or blocking tempting websites are better strategies to maintaining focus (Goldstein, 2016). To begin the process of eliminating distractions, go about your day as you normally would.

Every time your attention is taken from your task, make a note of what distracted you. Over a few days, you will see patterns or categories of distractions emerge. Identifying these will help you decide how to avoid them (Ent, M. R., Baumeister, R. F., & Vonasch, A. J., 2012). Remember, changing how you work will take time, so be patient as you eliminate distractions from your work day. Competing priorities and urgent tasks are often a fact of life for leaders, and sometimes, distractions will be inevitable. Self-discipline will help you maintain your focus in the face of nonessential interruptions.

Start Doing These Things Now to Increase Self-Discipline, the following steps can help you increase your self-control in the workplace:

1. Make time to make decisions. Decision-making is one of those tasks that often fall exclusively on to leaders. This includes everything from choosing how to allocate resources, focusing the priorities of your unit, and assigning work to each employee. Research has shown that decision-making is a tiring task, and that leaders find it difficult to retain self-control and focus after making important decisions (Goldstein, 2016). Treat

decision-making as any other task: give yourself an appropriate amount of time to focus on making the right choice as well as to recover from any stress that may result from this task. Forcing yourself to make important decisions while balancing other priorities will only ensure that you feel overwhelmed, contributing to low self-control.

2. Reduce the load. While decision-making may often fall to leaders, delegation is an important tool in preventing yourself from becoming overloaded. Where possible, have your employee's aid in decision making, either by gathering more information that will help you to make correct choices, or by offering their opinions and expertise (Goldstein, 2016). Not only does this reduce the amount of effort required from a leader, the literature also suggests that participation in some decision-making can improve the long-term self-discipline and motivation in employees. Delegating some of the work that goes into decision-making can be mutually beneficial for yourself and your employees.
3. Practice mindful meditation. Mindfulness meditation is gaining popularity within the world of work, and is often suggested as a solution to a host of organizational problems. However, good mindfulness training helps you to improve your focus by learning to concentrate on a fixed point, such as your breath, while letting emotions or thoughts pass by without effecting (Dapu, V. A. W., 2015). Daily mediation can have various positive effects for leaders, but in the case of self-discipline, individual mindfulness practice reduces impulsivity, helping you to retain your focus and control throughout the day.

The U.S. Office of Personnel Management defines performance management as the systemic process of: planning work and setting expectations, continually monitoring performance, developing the employee's capacity to perform, periodically *rating* performance in summary fashion, and rewarding good performance (Paauwe, J., 2004).

In an effective organization, work is planned in advance. This includes setting performance expectations and goals for individuals in order to channel efforts toward achieving organizational objectives (Armstrong, 2015).

Involving employees in the planning process helps them understand organizational goals, what needs to be done, why it needs to be done, and how well it should be done (Sabine, S and M, Frese., 2005; Armstrong, 2015). The fundamental basis of performance planning is the development of the performance plan for each employee. The performance plan outlines, in writing, the specific critical elements for which the employee will be held individually accountable during the appraisal period and the performance standards against which the employee's performance will be measured; i.e., how well the employee must perform on each element (Schuler, R S and Jackson, S E., 2007; Armstrong, 2015).

Critical elements and performance standards should be strategically linked, results-focused, measurable, understandable, verifiable, equitable, achievable, and provide for meaningful distinctions between levels of performance (Stephen, P. Robbins., 2011). Performance plans should also be flexible so that they can be adjusted for changing program objectives and work requirements. When used effectively, these plans can be beneficial working documents that

are discussed often, and not merely paperwork that is filed in a drawer and seen only when performance ratings are required.

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Performance standards are the expression of the performance thresholds, requirements or expectations that must be met to be appraised on a critical element at a particular level of performance (Storey, J., 2001). Performance standards must be focused on results and include credible measures such as:

Quality: “Addresses how well the employee or work unit is expected to perform the work and/or the accuracy, appearance, usefulness, or effectiveness of the final product. Measures may include error rates (such as the number or percentage of errors allowable per unit of work) and customer satisfaction rates (determined through a customer survey/feedback)”.

Quantity: “Addresses how much work the employee or work unit is expected to produce. Measures are expressed as a number of products or services expected, or as a general result to achieve”.

Timeliness: “Addresses how quickly, when, or by what date the employee or work unit is expected to produce the work”.

Cost-Effectiveness: “Addresses dollar savings or cost control. These measures should address specific resource levels or constraints (money, personnel, or time) that can generally be documented and measured. Cost-effectiveness measures may include such aspects of performance as maintaining or reducing unit costs, reducing the time it takes to produce or provide a product or service, or reducing waste”.

To develop specific measures, the rating official must determine the type or types of standards that can realistically be used to assess the outputs, outcomes, or results and progress toward goals for a given critical element, and then determine the measures and minimum results/outcomes/outputs that are required to achieve the specified level of performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Discipline is positive. “To cow the spirit, to subdue inclination, to compel obedience, to mortify the flesh, to make a subordinate perform an uncongenial task - these things are not disciplinary according to the development of power to recognize what one is about and to persistence in accomplishment”.

This study results that; “Time Discipline (X_1), Responsibility Discipline (X_2), and Regulator Discipline (X_3) have a significant effect on Performance Employee (Y) either partially or simultaneously. Time Discipline (X_1) variable has the most significant or dominant effect on Performance Employee (Y), self-discipline is best improved with frequent practice”.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

FUNDING

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

REFERENCE:

1. Armstrong, M and Baron, A. (2004). *Managing Performance: Performance management in action*, London, CIPD.
2. Anderson, D. W. (1999). *Personality, self-efficacy and managerial leadership behaviour*. Retrieved from ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Global.
3. Azman, I. et al. (2014). Effect of manager's role in performance based pay on employee outcomes. *Global Journal Al-Thaqafah*, 4(2), 41–58. Retrieved from www.gjat.my/gjat122014/6520140402.pdf
4. Bernadin, H. John and Joyce E.A. Russel. (2001). *Human Resources Management an Experimental Approach*, Mc. Graw Hill, Inc. International Edition
5. Boxall, P F and Purcell, J. (2003) *Strategy and Human Resource Management*, Basingstoke, Palgrave Macmillan
6. Brown, D. (2011). Performance management – can it ever work? *Manager*, Summer, p 16
7. Caiden and Becker G. (2005). *Human Resource Development*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
8. Campbell, J. P. (1999). The definition and measurement of performance in the new age. In D. R. Ilgen & E. D. Pulakos (Eds.), *The changing nature of performance. Implications for staffing, motivation, and development* (pp. 399–429). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
9. Creswell, John. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Third Edition. SAGE Publications India Pvt. Ltd.
10. Goldstein. (2016). *Great Leaders Exercise Self-Discipline*. Sigma. Self-Discipline in the Workplace. Assessment System. Inc. Publication.
11. Dapu, V. A. W. (2015). the Influence of Work Discipline , Leadership , and Motivation on Employee Performance At Pt . Trakindo Utama Manado. *Jurnal EMBA*, 3(3), 352–361.
12. Dessler, Gary. (1999). *Human Resource Management*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
13. Ent, M. R., Baumeister, R. F., & Vonasch, A. J. (2012). Power, leadership, and self-regulation. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 6(8), 619-630.
14. Emery, D. A. (1959). Managerial leadership through motivation by objectives. *Personnel Psychology*, 12(1), 65-79.
15. Frese, M., Garst, H., & Fay, D. (2000). Control and complexity in work and the development of personal initiative (PI): A four-wave longitudinal structural equation model of occupational socialization. University of Giessen: Manuscript submitted for publication.
16. Greer, C.R. (1995). *Strategy and Human Resources: A General Managerial Perspective*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall
17. Godard, J. (2004). A critical assessment of the high performance paradigm, *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 42 (2), pp 349–78
18. Guido Bertucci. (2005). *Human Resources for Effectivitive Public Administration in a Globalized Word*. Department of Economic and Social Affairs. United Nations, New York, NY 10017, USA.

19. Harris, P., Mongiello, M., (2001). Key performance indicators in European hotel properties: general managers' choice and company profiles. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 13 (3), 120–127.
20. Haines, V Y and St-Onge, S (2012) Performance management effectiveness: practices or context? *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23 (6), pp 1158–75
21. Ilgen, D. R., & Schneider, J. (1991). Performance measurement: A multi-discipline view. In C. L. Cooper & I. T. Robertson (Eds.), *International review of industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 6, pp. 71–108). Chichester: Wiley.
22. Karp, T. (2015). Is willpower important in acts of leadership? *Leadership*, 11(1), 20-35.
23. Lawler, E. E., & Mohrman, S. A. (2003). HR as a strategic partner: What does it take to make it happen? *Human Resource Planning*, 26(3), 15-29.
24. Mantzios, M. & Giannou, K. (2014). Group vs. single mindfulness meditation: Exploring avoidance, impulsivity, and weight management in two separate mindfulness mediation settings. *Applied Psychology: Health and Wellbeing*, 6 (2), 173-191.
25. Mangkunegara, A. P., & Octorend, T. R. (2015). Effect of Work Discipline, Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee Organizational Commitment in the Company (Case Study in PT. Dada Indonesia). *Universal Journal of Management*, 3(8), 318–328. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujm.2015.030803>
26. Motowidlo, S. J., & Schmit, M. J. (1999). Performance assessment in unique jobs. In D. R. Ilgen & E. D. Pulakos (Eds.), *The changing nature of job performance: Implications for staffing, motivation, and development* (pp. 56–86). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
27. Paauwe, J. (2004). *HRM and Performance: Achieving long-term viability*, Oxford, Oxford University Press
28. Pillay, R. (2009). Work satisfaction of professional nurses in south Africa: A comparative analysis of the public and private sectors. *Human Resources for Health* 17(15): 82-94.
29. Ramsay, H, Scholarios, D and Harley, B. (2000). Employees and high performance work systems: testing inside the black box, *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 38 (4), pp 501–31
30. Sarwani. (2016). The Effect Of Work Discipline And Work Environment On The Performance Of Employees. *Sinergi*, Volume 6, Number2 September 2016.
31. Sabine, S and M, Frese. (2005). *Performance Concepts and Performance Theory. Psychological Management of Individual Performance*. Edited by Sabine Sonnentag. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
32. Schuler, R S and Jackson, S E. (2007). *Strategic Human Resource Management*, 2nd edn, Oxford, Blackwell
33. Scott, W., Tiessen, P., (1999). Performance measurement and managerial teams. *Accounting Organizations and Society* 24, 263–285.
34. Shields, J. (2007). *Managing Employee Performance and Reward*, Port Melbourne, Cambridge University Press
35. Sparrow, P. (2013). Strategic HRM and employee engagement, in (eds) C Truss, R Deldridge, K Alfes, A Shantz and E Soane, *Employee Engagement in Theory and Practice*, London, Routledge, pp 99–115
36. Stephen, P. Robbins. (2011). *Fundamentals of Human Resource Management*. University of Groningen / Mzumbé University.
37. Stevens, J. (2005). *High Performance Wales: Real experiences, real success*, Cardiff, Wales Management Council

38. Storey, J. (2001). Human resource management today: an assessment, in (ed) J Storey, Human Resource Management: A critical text, 2nd edn, London, Thompson Learning, pp 3–20
39. Tangen, S., (2004). Performance Measurement: From Philosophy to Practice”, International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, Vol. 53, No. 8, pp. 726-37.
40. Thompson, M and Heron, P. (2005) Management capability and high performance work organization, International Journal of Human Resource Management, 16 (6), pp 1029–48
41. Van Scotter, J., Motowidlo, S. J., & Cross, T. C. (2000). Effects of task performance and contextual performance on systemic rewards. Journal of Applied Psychology, 85, 526–535.
42. Wortzel-Hoffman, N and Boltizar, S. (2007). Performance and development planning: a culture shift perspective, Organization Development Journal, 25 (2), pp 195–200
43. WorldatWork and Sibson. (2010). The State of Performance Management, Scottsdale AZ, WorldatWork
44. Youndt, M A. (2000). Human resource considerations and value creation: the mediating role of intellectual capital, Paper delivered at National Conference of US Academy of Management, Toronto, August
45. Zecca, G. Györkös, C., Becker, J., Massoudi, K., de Bruin, G. P., & Rossier, J. (2015). Validation of the French Utrecht Work Engagement Scale and its relationship with personality traits and impulsivity. European Review of Applied Psychology, 65(1), 19-28.